

Environmental awareness affects adoption of greener production systems: evidence from Italian winegrowers

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Abstract

This study investigates the environmental awareness of Italian winegrowers and its influence on adopting sustainable production protocols. Utilizing a multidimensional concept of environmental awareness, an online survey was conducted with 275 winegrowers from the Conegliano Valdobbiadene Prosecco Protected Designation of Origin area. Data were analyzed using Structural Equation Modeling and a Multinomial Probit Model, revealing four out of five dimensions as components of winegrowers' environmental awareness. The results demonstrated that increased environmental awareness significantly and positively affects the likelihood of adopting organic and integrated pest management protocols. These protocols reflect a growing commitment to environmentally responsible winemaking practices, which can yield substantial benefits in terms of ecological preservation and long-term sustainability. Moreover, results emphasize the importance of using the multidimensionality of the environmental awareness concept. Based on these findings, the study provides practical recommendations and policy implications for the wine sector.

Keywords: environmental awareness, SEM, multinomial probit, viticulture

1. Introduction

In recent years, the European Commission has promoted more sustainable agricultural production processes by encouraging the adoption of more sustainable practices through the Farm to Fork strategy¹. Indeed, agriculture is widely regarded as a major source of environmental pollution due to the overuse of pesticides and chemicals, resulting in a loss of functional biodiversity, land degradation, and contamination of air, water, and soil (Jhariya et al., 2019). This is especially true in the wine industry, where disease and pest pressure force winegrowers to use pesticides extensively (Marsala et al., 2020), slowing the adoption of more sustainable production systems.² Winegrowers are being pushed to adopt more sustainable production systems in order to limit the environmental and social damage caused by the rapid spread of viticulture (OIV, 2016; Galletto and Barisan, 2018). However, even though several environmentally friendly viticulture practices exist, and numerous political incentives provided by public policy interventions such as Rural Development Programs have pushed the adoption of more sustainable production protocols, several factors, such as farmers' personal traits, environmental variability, and economic and political aspects (Feliciano, 2022; Raimondo et al., 2021; Aregay et al., 2018), slowing the adoption of more sustainable viticultural practices.

Recent research emphasizes the significance of psychological/behavioral dimensions in influencing farmers' propensity to adopt sustainable agricultural practices (Despotovic et al., 2021). Environmental awareness (EA) is regarded as the first important prerequisite that people should acquire in order to re-orient their behaviors in a pro-environmental/social direction since it reflects people's concern for and knowledge of the environmental consequences of their actions, (Fu et al., 2020). So far, several studies have been conducted over the last few decades to investigate the relationship between environmental awareness and behavior for various groups of people (Fu et al., 2020), including students (Sekhokoane et al., 2017), project managers (Zhang and Zhou, 2016), citizens (Liobikiene and Juknys, 2016), households (Lillemo, 2014), consumers (Kikuchi-Uehara et al., 2016), and heads of manufacturing companies (Zsoka, 2008). Despotovic and colleagues (2021) have recently provided a theoretical and methodological framework for measuring environmental awareness as a multidimensional concept, with a focus on farmers' environmental awareness and its role in adopting cleaner agricultural practices.

¹ https://food.ec.europa.eu/horizontal-topics/farm-fork-strategy_en

² In Italy, less than 22% of the total area is organic. <https://www.sinab.it/reportannuali/anticipazioni-bio-cifre-2022>

However, no studies have tested in Italy environmental awareness as a multidimensional concept, particularly in a specific sector, such as viticulture, where more sustainable production systems are desperately needed. As a result, an empirical study will be accomplished among winegrowers in the Conegliano Valdobbiadene Prosecco PDO, a DOCG (Controlled and Guaranteed Designation of Origin), which is historically Italy's most important area for the production of Prosecco's sparkling wines (Rossetto et al., 2011; Pomarici et al., 2019; Galletto, Barisan, 2021). The relationship between the EA of Prosecco winegrowers and the adoption of agricultural systems can be useful in understanding whether and to what extent environmental awareness influences the adoption of sustainable production systems. As a result, once environmental awareness is measured as a multidimensional concept, following the framework of Despotovic et al., (2021), the current study attempts to answer the following two research questions: RQ1: "Which EA dimension (environmental knowledge, environmental attitudes, connectedness with nature, environmental behavior, and biospheric concern) best describes Italian winegrowers' environmental awareness?" and RQ2: "Does winegrowers' environmental awareness in the Conegliano Valdobbiadene Prosecco Protected Designation of Origin (CVPP) area influence their adoption of more sustainable production systems?" By using Structural Equation Modeling and a Multinomial Probit Model, this paper empirically tested the predictive power of environmental awareness in influencing winegrowers' likelihood of adopting organic and integrated pest management protocols. Results provide valuable insights into potential drivers for the adoption of sustainable production systems in Italian viticulture.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: In Section 2, the theoretical background of the study is provided while Section 3 refers to the methodology. Results are described in Section 4 and discussed in Section 5. Conclusions are finally summarized in Section 6.

2. Theoretical background

2.1 Dimensions of Environmental Awareness

The complexity and multifaceted nature of environmental awareness made difficult to provide a unique definition of environmental awareness (Cynk, 2017; Baumgart-Getz et al., 2012; Ali, 2015). Despotovic and colleagues (2021) developed and tested a latent construct of farmers' EA as a multidimensional concept, including rational/experiential and emotional/psychological domains. This sub-section aims to provide the reader with a brief description of the recent multidimensional concept of EA developed by Despotovic and colleagues (2021). The construct includes five dimensions of EA, such as: i) environmental knowledge (Env know), ii) biospheric concern (Bios conc), iii) connectedness to nature (INS), iv) environmental attitudes (NEP), and v) environmental

behavior (Env beh) (Despotovic et al., 2021). The first dimension of EA, environmental knowledge, refers to the objective farmers' understanding of local, regional, and global environmental issues, as well as potential solutions (Bamberg and Moser, 2007).

The second and the third dimensions, such as biospheric concern and connection to nature respectively, include personal values concerning psychological and emotional aspects. Personal values are identified as mental principles that unconsciously guide the decision-making process of a person (Dietz et al., 2005; Siebert et al., 2006).

According to Hansla and colleagues (2008), certain value orientations are effective predictors of pro-environmental attitudes and behavior. Tuna (2004) discovered that EA differs between people with anthropocentric beliefs and people with biospheric beliefs. While the former (anthropocentric vision) believes that the environment is dominated by people and that nature has value for human use only (Nordlund and Garvill, 2003), the latter (biospheric vision) believes that nature has value for itself and for human use (Tuna, 2004).

The assessment of EA, according to Mayer and McPherson Frantz (2004), requires knowledge of the individual's connectedness to nature, which refers to people's innate tendency to see themselves as part of nature (Wilson, 1984; Tam, 2013). It is well known that people who feel more connected to nature are more likely to engage in pro-environmental behavior (Gosling and Williams, 2010). Indeed, Suzuki (2022) confirmed that if a person feels completely connected to nature, he or she perceives environmental destruction as self-destruction. Environmental attitudes, defined as psychological preferences for the environment, are another (fourth) determinant of the EA (Milfont and Duckitt, 2010), as they can be used to predict environmentally responsible behavior (Despotovic et al., 2021). The general attitude of the respondent toward the environment was not addressed since the current study analyses respondent's attitudes toward viticulture, by adapting, for the first time, the item of the New Ecological Paradigm (NEP) scale (Dunlap et al. 2000) to viticulture.

Environmental behavior (the fifth dimension) – defined as any intentional or unintentional action that may have an impact on the environment (Macovei, 2015) - is regarded as a critical domain that significantly reflects farmers' EA.

2.2 Measures of Environmental Awareness

The current sub-section aims to briefly describe how each of the five Environmental Awareness (EA) dimensions were measured in this study context. The objective environmental knowledge was measured by asking respondents to list all environmental problems they know. As a result, a higher number of environmental problems corresponds to a higher environmental knowledge score.

Winegrowers' environmental values are quantified by measuring both biospheric concern and connectedness with nature. While the Environmental Motives Scale (EMS) (Schultz, 2000) can be used to assess biospheric concern, the Inclusion of Nature in the Self Scale (INS) (Schultz, 2001) can be used to assess one's connection to nature. Accordingly, biospheric concern is assessed by asking winegrowers to rank from 1 (the least concerned) to 6 (the most concerned) how much they are concerned about the impact of environmental problems on given areas: all children, viticulture, me, bees, my future, and all people. Then, for each individual, we added up the ranks assigned to viticulture and bees to generate a biospheric concern score ranging from 3 to 11, with 11 indicating the highest possible biospheric concern and 3 indicating the lowest one.

The INS scale adapted from Schultz (2001) and Despotovic and colleagues (2021) has been used to measure winegrowers' connectedness to nature. Respondents were asked to choose one of the five images with different levels of overlap between one circle representing the individual and the other representing nature. The New Ecological Paradigm (NEP) scale, developed by Dunlap et al., 2000, has been adapted to assess the viticulture attitudes of winegrowers.

Overall, 15 items have been adapted to viticulture and evaluated using a five-point Likert scale, with "1" indicating "strongly disagree" and "5" indicating "strongly agree." The scale of negatively worded items was reversed prior to statistical analysis³. Finally, to capture intentional actions taken by winegrowers to benefit the environment, we measured the environmental behaviour with a single item as proposed by Despotovic and colleagues (2021): "Have you changed your behaviour due to environmental reasons?".

2.3 Study area and problem statement

The CVPP is located 50 kilometers north of Venice in the Province of Treviso (Veneto region). Since 2009, it has been recognized as the most significant production area of Prosecco's Denominations of Origin in terms of: i) vineyard surface, ii) number of winegrowers, and iii) annual wine production (Rossetto et al., 2011; Boatto et al., 2022).

In 2021, the CVPP's vineyard area spanned 8,700 hectares, some of which cover an area recognized as a UNESCO World Heritage Site in 2019. The area predominantly consists of small and medium-

³ The item description is provided in Table A of the Appendix

sized viticultural firms, while large (between 5 and 10 hectares) and very large (more than 10 hectares) holdings constitute a smaller share. The total number of winegrowers is 3,351, integrated into a system characterized by a multiplicity of organizational forms and supply specializations: 1,272 are members of cooperative wineries, independent wine growers (1,674) deliver their grapes to winemakers, and there are vintners (244) and private bottling wineries (161). The latter also hold a limited share of vineyards and are categorized as winegrowers, transformer bottlers, and plain bottlers according to their degree of specialization. Most of the vineyards are family-owned and span less than 3 hectares. In 2021, the production of base wine for CVPP reached 785,275 hectoliters (equivalent to 104.7 million bottles sold).

In recent decades, rapidly growing international interest in Prosecco (Rossetto et al., 2011) has led to a significant increase in vineyard cultivation in the municipalities of the CVPP zone. From 2007 to 2012, more than 1,064 hectares and between 2013 and 2017, an additional 1,688 hectares of land were planted with new vineyards (Basso, 2019; Boatto et al., 2022). Despite being a form of agriculture, the expansion of such intensive land-use practices has significant territorial and social implications, including the replacement of other crops, environmental and landscape degradation, and environmental changes, particularly in areas of high environmental value (Bianchin, Galletto, 2009). The rapid expansion of new vineyards implies a growing public awareness of the negative consequences of widespread chemical usage on health, the environment (air, water, and soil), and the landscape. This also suggests an increasing concern about the ecological damage caused by the creation of new vineyards in high-risk areas. To mitigate the negative effects of rapid viticulture expansion on the environment and society, winegrowers are encouraged to adopt more environmentally friendly production methods (Galletto and Barisan, 2018).

In 2011, the CVPP's Consortium implemented a voluntary Viticultural Protocol based on the winegrowers' compliance with agronomic and phytopathological rules, which were more restrictive regarding the use of active ingredients (e.g., drastic elimination of Mancozeb, Folpet, etc.) than the national one. Since 2019, the use of the herbicide glyphosate has also been prohibited. The CVPP's Consortium has adopted a new certification scheme (Integrated Pest Management, or SQNPI) since 2019, promoted by the Italian Agricultural Ministry. In 2021, 43.7% of the bottled produced has been certified as SQNPI, 54% as the Viticulture Protocol, and 2.3% of bottles has been certified as organic (Boatto et al., 2022). However, little is known about the factors influencing the adoption of more sustainable production practices, especially the role of EA in winegrowers' propensity to adopt sustainable production systems. As a result, research into the environmental awareness of winegrowers in the CVPP district would be useful not only for the study area but would also provide

new valuable insights about the role of EA as a multidimensional concept on the probability to adopt sustainable viticultural practices in Italy.

3.Method

3.1. Data collection and survey development

EA was measured on a sample of winegrowers in the Veneto region's CVPP area. The survey was completed anonymously and voluntarily by winegrowers. The questionnaire created with Google Forms has three sections: i) winegrower and vineyard information, ii) five dimensions of winegrower's EA, and iii) adoption of specific production protocol⁴ (i.e. Organic protocol, Integrated Pest Management (IPM) protocol, DOPG Viticulture protocol, and none protocol). A pilot study with 35 farmers was used to evaluate the final version of the questionnaire. Minor changes were made in response to the pilot study participants' suggestions. 2,946 winegrowers have received an online questionnaire through email, along with a formal cover letter outlining the goal of the scientific investigation (the sum of the 4 email lists contained 88% of the CVPP's winegrower population). The winegrowers to whom the online study was sent were identified as two types of winegrowers: those who deliver their grapes to wine cooperatives (i.e., Valdobbiadene, Colli del Soligo, and Cantina di Conegliano e Vittorio Veneto), accounting for 43.2% of firms, and those who deliver their grapes to private wineries (56.8%) (Boatto et al., 2022). Data collection was supported by a few reminders from the cooperatives and the CVPP Consortium. Before recruiting participants, we carried out an a priori power analysis to estimate the required sample size for detecting an effect size (in terms of correlation between constructs) equal to 0.18, with an alpha = 0.05 and a power of 0.90 (Faul et al., 2009). The estimated sample size required for the study was N = 260. Overall, 289 winegrowers answered back the questionnaire, with a response rate of 9.3%. The total sample size after discarding 14 incomplete questionnaires was 275. The survey's sections addressing the use of EA elements from the literature were translated into Italian. The survey was carried out during July and September 2021.

3.2. Data analysis

Two different methods, the Structural Equation Model (SEM) and the Multinomial Probit Logit (MPL) will be used to answer the first (RQ1) and the second (RQ2) research questions, respectively. Despostovic et al. (2021) stated that the EA is a multidimensional term that encompasses five related

⁴ A description of each production protocol is provided in Table B of the Appendix

but separate dimensions: environmental knowledge (Env Know), biospheric concern (Bios Conc), connectivity to nature (INS), environmental attitudes (NEP), and environmental behavior (Env Beh). To know which dimension (environmental knowledge, environmental attitudes, connectedness with nature, environmental behavior, and biospheric concern) best describes Italian winegrowers' EA, we used the structural equation model which takes into consideration the multidimensional aspect of the EA notion (Despotovic et al., 2021). SEM can be used to construct and quantify theoretical concepts such as personalities, attitudes, motives, emotions, and abilities that aren't always easy to observe and assess (Hoyle, 2012). The internal consistency of the EA construct and its applicability for vineyard farms were statistically validated in this study using SEM. Moreover, SEM was also helpful in developing the latent winegrowers' EA construct, analysing and combining the data provided by various measurement tools, and finally in generating the latent winegrowers' EA construct. We estimated the following measurement model (equation 1) including the relationship between the latent variable and its components, for the i -th respondent:

$$\mathbf{x}_i = \boldsymbol{\gamma}EA_i + u_i \quad i=1, \dots, 275 \quad (1)$$

where the latent construct EA is linked to the p -vector of the observed measurement instrument \mathbf{x} (Env_Know, Bios_Conc, INS, NEP, and Env_Beh) through the p -vector of parameters $\boldsymbol{\gamma}$ (or loadings), while u is the error component. Then, we used an ANOVA test to compare the differences in EA between groups of winegrowers that adopt different production protocols or none of them, characterized by different requirements to be accomplished by farmers for reducing the production environmental impact (i.e., Organic, DOCG Viticulture protocol, Integrated Pest Management (IPM) control protocol, and none protocol).

Lastly, in order to know if the adoption of different production protocols by winegrowers is influenced by EA (the RQ2), we implemented a multinomial probit (MNP) model. The MNP is suitable⁵ in this study since the dependent variable is discrete and also characterized by multiple (not ordered) options (Cameron and Trivedi, 2005).

The MNP model is expressed for the i -th winegrowers as:

$$\pi_{ik}(Y_i = k) = \frac{e^{\alpha + \beta_k(EA_i) + \gamma_k Z_i}}{1 + \sum_{j=1}^{K-1} e^{\alpha + \beta_j(EA_i) + \gamma_j Z_i}}, k \leq K \quad (2)$$

⁵In this study, the MNP is preferred to multinomial logit, since the former performs better than the latter, having lower AIC and BIC values.

where π_{ik} represents the probability that the winegrower adopts the k production protocol ($j=k$) among the K different production alternatives (conventional, organic, IPM, DOCG Viticulture Protocol). EA represents winegrower's Environmental Awareness, \mathbf{Z} is a matrix of socio-demographics (gender, age, education, years of experience) and structural (hectares and slope) characteristics.

The estimated parameters β and γ reflect the effect of the explanatory variables on the probability ratio between the k production protocol and the $j=K$ production protocol, that here is represented by the conventional practices.

4.Results

4.1 Descriptive statistics

The final sample consisted of 275 respondents. Traditional sociodemographic and structural information (Table 1) shows that respondents were mainly male (79%), younger than 54 years old (59%), and without a university degree (75%). As for the structural characteristics of the vineyard, the size ranges between a minimum of 0.163 hectares to 105 hectares (the maximum value). Most vineyards (82%) have a slope lower than 30% while the 18% are located in a more sloping area (more than 30% of slope). Furthermore, DOCG Viticulture Protocol (48%), followed by IPM (45%), is the most widely used production protocol. Only 3% of vineyards are organic, and 4% have declared that they follow a conventional production protocol.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics of winegrowers and structural characteristics.

Variable	Variable description/Frequency (%)	Mean	St.dev.	Min	Max
Production protocol	1=Organic (3%)	NA	NA	1.0	4.0
	2=None Protocol (4%)				
	3= DOCG Viticulture Protocol (48%)				
	4= IPM (Integrated Pest Management) (45%)				
Environmental Awareness	Standardized variable	0	1	-2.19	1.86
Gender	0= Male (79%)	0.21	NA	0	2.0
	1=Female (20%)				
	2=Prefer not to say (1%)				
Age	18-24 (1%)	4.22	NA	1.0	7.0
	25-34 (9%)				
	35-44 (21%)				
	45-54 (28%)				
	55-64 (24%)				
	65-74 (13%)				
	75 e più (4%)				
Education	University degree (25%)	2.89	NA	1.0	4.0
	High school (46%)				
	Secondary School (22%)				
	Primary School (7%)				
Vineyard size	Hectares	5.13	8.87	0.163	105
Slope	0= Less than 30% (82%)	0.18	NA	0	1.0
	1= More than 30% (18%)				

Table 2 shows the descriptive statistics of the measurements used in the development of the winegrower EA construct. The number of environmental problems asserted by winegrowers indicates their environmental knowledge. More precisely, the greater the number of stated environmental problems corresponds to, a higher environmental knowledge score. The average number of correctly stated problems was 3.2, with a minimum of 1 and a maximum of 5. Indeed, each participant correctly identified at least one environmental issue that humanity is currently dealing with. The most common response was to climate change and related issues such as global warming and extreme weather conditions. As stated above, while the EMS scale (Schultz, 2000) is used to assess biospheric concern, the Inclusion of Nature in the Self Scale (INS) (Schultz, 2001) is used to assess the connection to nature. Overall, 35% of respondents ranked viticulture and bees as the least important reasons for environmental concern (biospheric score = 3), which is slightly higher than the percentage of winegrowers who expressed the most concern for viticulture and bees (30%), thus showing the maximum score for biospheric concern (biospheric score = 11).

According to the adapted INS scale, 30% of respondents felt completely connected to nature. The winegrowers who felt completely united with nature chose perfectly overlapping circles, showing complete harmony between the individual and nature. Many respondents (36%) chose nearly perfectly overlapping circles. In comparison, only 1% of winegrowers felt completely disconnected from nature. The NEP scale was adapted to viticulture and used to assess winegrowers' environmental attitudes. The average aggregate score of the 15 NEP items was 3.04. The final EA component, environmental behavior, was assessed using self-reported changes in respondents' behavior. More than 85% of respondents said they have changed their behavior due to environmental concerns.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of environmental awareness measures.

Measure	Description	Mean	Std.dev.
Environmental Knowledge (Env_know)	Number of reported environmental issues	3.2	1.29
Biospheric concern (Bios_conc)	Aggregation of responses to two biospheric object (i.e. viticulture and bees) of concerns (min 3, max 11)	6.6	2.24
INS	1= completely detached to 5=completely united with nature	3.9	0.88
NEP	Average aggregate NEP score where (1=Not agree, 5= Totally agree)	3.04	1.14
Previous change in environmental behaviour (Env_beh)	0=no, 1=yes	0.86	N.A.

Note: N.A.: not applicable

4.2 Environmental awareness construct

The results of the measurement model demonstrate the validity and suitability of the estimated construct for assessing the level of EA in winegrowers. Except for the dimension of connectedness with nature (INS), all of the selected indicators, such as environmental knowledge (Env know), environmental attitudes (NEP), environmental behavior (Env beh), and biospheric concern (Bios conc), contribute to defining the latent EA construct, as shown in Figure 1. The coefficient (factor loadings) between EA and each element ranged from 0.705 for environmental knowledge to 0.155 for biospheric concern. The results indicate that the indicator that makes the greatest contribution to winegrowers' EA construct is environmental knowledge while connectedness to nature (INS) does not contribute to the EA latent construct.

Figure 1. Environmental awareness as latent construct.

Note: * $p < 0.10$ ** $p < 0.05$. The figure shows SEM results with the contribution of the selected measures to defining the latent environmental awareness (EA) construct. Environmental knowledge (Env_know) has the highest contribution (factor loadings = 0.705), followed by environmental attitudes (NEP) and environmental behavior (Env_Beh) whose factor loadings are 0.245, 0.256, respectively. Biospheric concern (Bios_conc) has the lowest contribution (0.155) while connectedness to nature (INS) has a non-significant contribution.

Once we validated the winegrowers' EA construct, we compared the estimated values for groups of winegrowers categorized based on whether they adopted specific environmentally friendly production protocols. The results (Table 3) show that the level of EA is the highest in winegrowers who adopted the organic protocol (0.029), followed by the integrated pest management control protocol (0.003) and DOCG Viticulture Protocol (-0.003), which are not statistically different. Finally, winegrowers who do not adopt a production protocol showed the lowest level of EA.

Table 3. Anova test of production protocol difference in level of environmental awareness.

Production protocol	Margin	Std. Err.	Groups
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Organic	0.029	.0129	
Conventional	-0.023	.0110	
DOCG Viticulture Protocol	-0.003	.0032	A
Integrated pest management control protocol	0.003	.0033	A

Note: Margins sharing a letter in the group label are not significantly different at the 10% level.

4.3 Multinomial Probit results

Results of the MNP regression are presented in Table 4. Environmental awareness shows a significant and positive effect on the probability to adopt the organic protocol of production, meaning that the higher the environmental awareness of winegrowers, the higher the probability of adopting an organic production protocol (0.851 $p=0.014$). The probability to adopt the organic protocol is also positively affected by control variables, such as gender (1.101 $p=0.082$) and education (0.851 $p=0.025$). While the gender of the winegrower positively affects the probability to adopt the DOCG Viticulture Protocol (1.251 $p=0.010$) and the slope of the vineyard negatively affects it (-0.992 $p=0.016$), the EA shows a non-significant effect on the probability to adopt such Viticulture Protocol. Conversely, the EA significantly and positively affects the probability to adopt the IPM production protocol (0.444 $p=0.050$) which decreases if the vineyard is large (-0.363 $p=0.028$) and if it has a slope greater than 30% (-1.460 $p<0.001$).

Table 4. Multinomial probit regression

<i>Organic/None protocol</i>	<i>DOCG Viticulture Protocol/None protocol</i>	<i>IPM/None protocol</i>
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EA	0.851** (0.345)	0.252 (0.227)	0.444* (0.227)
Gender	1.101* (0.632)	1.251* (0.487)	0.659 (0.500)
Age	0.378 (0.275)	-0.053 (0.198)	-0.122 (0.199)
Education	0.851** (0.379)	0.439 (0.301)	0.098 (0.299)
Vineyard size (ha)	-0.234 (0.205)	-0.229 (0.165)	-0.363** (0.165)
Slope	-0.942 (0.587)	-0.992** (0.411)	-1.460*** (0.412)
Cons	-4.179* (2.215)	1.138 (1.590)	2.671* (1.598)

Note. None protocol is the base outcome. Robust standard error is in brackets. *p<10%; **p<5% ***p<1%.

Figure 2 is a graphic illustration of the effect of the winegrower's environmental awareness on the probability to adopt a protocol of production. The Figure clearly shows that the increase in winegrower's EA increases the probability to adopt Organic and IPM protocols of production.

Figure 2. Effect of the environmental awareness on the probability of adopting a production protocol.

5. Discussion

The complexity of the concept of environmental awareness has meant that it has been difficult to measure it in its entirety for a long time. However, a few years ago, Despotovic and colleagues (2021) tackled the intricate problem associated with environmental awareness (EA) by providing a theoretical and methodological framework for measuring the multi-dimensional concept of farmers' environmental awareness. The aforementioned approach is quite recent and has not been widely applied in empirical studies, particularly within the viticulture sector. Consequently, our study stands out for its unique application of this novel concept and methodology in viticulture, analyzing winegrowers' environmental awareness. This includes aspects such as environmental knowledge, biospheric concern, connectedness to nature, environmental attitudes, and environmental behavior.

Except for the connectedness to nature, all dimensions of EA affect winegrowers' EA, with environmental knowledge having the greatest impact. This is consistent with the findings of Despotovic and colleagues (2021), who identified environmental knowledge as the primary dimension of the EA and thus an important driver of the adoption of sustainable agricultural practices in Serbia. Liobikiene and Poskus (2019) and Kokkinen (2013) emphasize the importance of environmental knowledge. The latter considers knowledge to be useful in making people aware of nature's limitations and threats to natural systems. Attitudes, as measured by the NEP scale, and environmental behavior are the second and third most important dimensions of the EA. The average aggregated NEP score for the sampled winegrowers is 3.04, slightly lower than the scores calculated by Despotovic et al. (2021) for Serbian farmers and Denis and Pereira (2017) for Romanian urban households. Olli et al. (2001) and Chen et al. (2011) argue that higher NEP scale values promote environmentally responsible behavior.. Conversely, Whitmarsh and O'Neill (2010) state that high NEP values do not impact environmentally responsible behavior. In this study, winegrowers accept the new environmental paradigm without rejecting the dominant social paradigm, mirroring the findings of Despotovic and colleagues (2021). This is likely because many people, especially those adhering to the DSP paradigm, think that nature is an infinite resource (Denis and Pereira, 2017).

In terms of environmental behavior, our study found that winegrowers who stated that they had changed their own behavior for environmental reasons had a high EA. One possible explanation for the positive relationship between environmental behavior and EA is that people who volunteer to help the environment are more aware of its importance and concerned about it (Bamberg and Rees, 2015). Consistent with Despotovic and colleagues (2021), the biospheric concern dimension demonstrated the lowest contribution to the latent construct of winegrowers' environmental awareness. However, Milfont et al. (2006) and Price and Leviston (2014) emphasized the crucial role of biospheric concern as a predictor of environmental practices. Conversely to several studies in the literature (Braun and Dierkes, 2017; Lokhorst et al., 2014), including Despotovic et al. (2021), connectedness with nature

does not determine winegrowers' environmental awareness. Regarding the second research question (RQ2), results from the MNP underscore the significance of winegrowers' environmental awareness in adopting certain sustainable production protocols.

Even though EA has a non-significant effect on DOCG Viticulture Protocol, a higher level of EA is associated with a higher likelihood of adopting certain production protocols (i.e. Organic, IPM). One possible explanation for this non-significant effect is that reasons other than environmental concern (e.g. economic benefits) might affect the adoption of such production protocol (Basso, 2019; Galletto and Barisan, 2018). Going back to the organic protocol, our findings are consistent with those of Karki et al. (2011), who discovered that environmental awareness is one of the major factors influencing farmers' decisions to convert to organic tea production. Kociszewski et al., (2020) discovered that environmental awareness is one of the social values that can help spread organic production. This means that farmers who care about the environment can more easily adopt a production system in which pesticides and chemicals are drastically (i.e. organic) or significantly (IPM) reduced. As for the adoption of organic production protocol, our findings are consistent with several previous studies (Ayuya et al., 2015; Hoang, 2021) where higher educated female are more likely to adopt organic protocol of production. As for the DOCG Viticulture Protocol, also gender and slope affect the probability to adopt this production protocol. While female winegrowers also increase the probability of adopting the DOCG Viticulture Protocol, this likelihood decreases if the vineyard is on a steep slope. The slope, combined with a larger vineyard size, negatively impacts the probability of adopting the IPM production protocol. Winegrowers managing vineyards with steep slopes, where costs are inherently high, perceive the adoption of IPM certification as an additional cost. Similarly, full compliance with the Viticulture Protocol, a more restrictive document than IPM, under climatic conditions conducive to diseases like downy mildew and powdery mildew, which require more vine protection interventions, may deter winegrowers from adopting it. For organic viticulture, these arguments are less persuasive, as deep-rooted socially based beliefs exist within a particular cohort of winemakers. Furthermore, transitioning to newer, less familiar methods of pest control appears riskier for higher value-added wines, such as those produced in the steep-slope Rive sub-appellation (Boatto et al., 2022), making vine growers more cautious in adopting these methods.

6. Conclusions

The European Commission is pushing the adoption of more sustainable agricultural production processes through the Farm to Fork strategy, especially for viticulture, where the use of pesticides is extremely high (Marsala et al., 2020). Recent studies emphasize the significance of environmental

awareness in influencing farmers' propensity to adopt sustainable agricultural practices (Despotovic et al., 2021). The current study aims at measuring the EA of winegrowers in the CVPP area as a multidimensional concept and it aims at analyzing if the EA affects the probability to adopt a more sustainable protocol of production.

Statistical analysis by employing SEM was performed on five dimensions (environmental knowledge, environmental behaviour, environmental attitudes, connectedness to nature and biospheric concern) of the EA. Then, a MNP model was performed to analyse a possible effect of the EA on the probability to adopt a more sustainable protocol of production. As for the first research question (RQ1), the results showed that except for the “connectedness with nature”, all dimensions are components of the winegrowers' EA. The latter significantly and positively affect the probability to adopt both organic and IPM production protocols (RQ2). This study may provide significant insights for policymakers to help design policy strategies for increasing environmental awareness of winegrowers since it highlights what aspects of environmental awareness have the most impact on the adoption of sustainable farming systems in viticulture. Therefore, political and practical implications are provided. The findings are very helpful to understand drivers or barriers for reducing the environmental impact of viticulture as this research can facilitate policy development strategies for designing appropriate intervention measures. Our findings, for example, emphasize the importance of environmental knowledge. As a consequence, by improving the environmental knowledge of winegrowers through information campaigns or technical assistance services could enhance the adoption of more environmentally friendly practices. Indeed, advisory services should provide instructions on more sustainable viticulture practices, emphasizing their importance, as well as the importance of protection of nature.. This will encourage winegrowers' desire for environmental protection and stabilize behavioural changes, potentially reducing the negative environmental impacts of viticulture in the CVPP area, which is also a major goal of the European Union.

Despite its contributions, the current study has some limitations that could lead to future research in this field. Firstly, the observations are limited to a specific Italian viticultural area, making the results unsuitable for inference. Furthermore, additional variables (e.g., labour and machine intensity) may influence the likelihood of adopting sustainable production protocols, which the current study did not take into account. As a result, future research may examine a more representative sample with a larger number of observations. Moreover, a more comprehensive model, without omitting variables, could be performed in future research, analysing the impact of EA on the likelihood of adopting sustainable production practices in other agricultural sectors as well.

Ethical statement

Before starting the questionnaire, participants were informed about the anonymity of data collection and signed the informed consent form, declaring that they were at least 18 years old.

This study was performed in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and was approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee at the corresponding author's institution. The data were analyzed anonymously.

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